

Chemical speciation of ternary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with L-phenylalanine and maleic acid in TX100-water mixtures

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Abstract : Chemical speciation of ternary systems of M^{II} [M = Pb, Cd and Hg] with L-phenylalanine (L) and maleic acid (X) in 0.0–2.5% v/v Triton X-100 (TX100)-water mixtures has been studied using pH-metric method at a temperature of 303.0 K and an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹. The ternary species confirmed are MLXH₂, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Pb^{II} and MLX₂H₃, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Cd^{II} and ML₂XH₂, ML₂XH and MLX₂ for Hg^{II}. The trend in the variation of stability and concentrations of the ternary species with the mole fraction of the medium was explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces. Distribution of the species with pH at different compositions of TX100-water mixtures was also presented. The formation of various binary and ternary complexes has been inferred from the corresponding titration curves. The extra stability of ternary complexes compared to their binary analogues is explained based difference in stability ($\Delta \log K$) approach.

Keywords : pH-Metric method, ternary complexes, L-phenylalanine, maleic acid, Triton X-100.

Introduction

The toxicity, bio-availability, bioaccumulation, biodegradability, persistence, mobility, solubility, extractability and many other critical properties depend on the form and nature of the chemical species^{1–3}. Speciation analysis or simply speciation is in fact the determination of these distinct species. Speciation has gained gradually a very wide recognition as vital component of Inorganic chemistry, since the knowledge of the total concentration of an element in specific area is often inadequate to explain its various different roles and properties. The term speciation encompasses usually two slightly different connotations of speciation, functional one and the operational one. These two may overlap but they are not at all identical. Functionally we may identify and distinguish between species that are, for example, available to plants or ecotoxic species of an element that are more easily exchangeable in mineral surfaces than others, etc.

Heavy metals and metalloids can be involved in a series of complex chemical and biological interactions^{4,5}.

The most important factors which affect their mobility are pH, sorbent nature, presence and concentration of organic and inorganic ligands, including humic and fulvic acids, root exudates and nutrients⁶. Lead is known to have toxic effects on membrane structure and functions⁷. Erythrocytes have high affinity for lead and are more vulnerable to oxidative damage than many other cells⁸. Cd^{II} ion is an abundant nonessential element present in food, water and the environment and it accumulates in human tissues, particularly in the lungs, liver, kidneys, brain, heart and testes⁹. Cd^{II} can induce oxidative stress and cause oxidative disorders in both animal cells¹⁰ and plants¹¹. Oxidative stress contributes to the development of various pathologies in the organism^{12,13}. Humans have increased the amount of mercury that is actively cycling in the environment by mining, industrial activities and combustion of fossil fuel. Once released into the environment, Hg undergoes redox, biological and phase transformations. Uncertainty about the origin and magnitude of emissions to the atmosphere presents challenges to the scientists and policy-makers^{14,15}.

L-Phenylalanine (Phe) is biologically converted into L-tyrosine. L-Tyrosine in turn is converted into L-DOPA, which is further converted into dopamine, nor epinephrine, and epinephrine. Phenylalanine is converted to cinnamic acid by the action of enzyme phenylalanine ammonialyase¹⁶. Phenylalanine uses the same active transport channel as tryptophan to cross the blood-brain barrier, and in large quantities, interferes with the production of serotonin. Industrially maleic acid (MA) is derived by hydrolysis of maleic anhydride. Maleic acid is an industrial raw material for the production of glyoxylic acid by ozonolysis. The major industrial use of maleic acid is its conversion to fumaric acid. Maleic acid and fumaric acid do not spontaneously interconvert because rotation around a carbon carbon double bond is not energetically favorable. However, it is possible by photolysis in the presence of a small amount of bromine.

The effect of micelles on overall reaction rates and equilibria depends upon the incorporation of solutes into the micellar pseudo phase. The second reason is that the species with lower charge or high hydrophobicity are stabilized in the micellar pseudo phase. So, metal ligand combinations resulting in neutral complexes will be favored. It has been demonstrated that water insoluble metal chelates can be solubilised with a micellar solution of non-ionic surfactant such as TX100. This solubilisation technique is frequently utilized in analytical procedures¹⁷. Since TX100 is a non-ionic surfactant, it is expected to destabilize the charged species in aqueous solutions. In recent years modeling studies involving ternary complexes have gained popularity¹⁸⁻²¹. Hence, in the present study speciation of ternary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with L-phenylalanine and maleic acid in TX100-water mixture was investigated.

Experimental

0.05 mol L⁻¹ solutions of L-phenylalanine (Loba, India) and maleic acid (Loba, India) were prepared in deionised triple-distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid concentration to increase the solubility. TX100 (Merck, India) was used as received. Sodium nitrate (Qualigens, India) of 2 mol L⁻¹ was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. Solutions of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} nitrates (0.1 mol L⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving appropriate quantities of G.R. grade (E.

Merck, Germany) salts in triple distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ acid (HNO₃) to suppresses the hydrolysis of metal ions. Nitric acid (Merck, India) of 0.2 mol L⁻¹ and sodium hydroxide (Merck, India) of 0.4 mol L⁻¹ were also prepared. All these solutions were standardized using standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification²². The strengths of the alkali and the mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method^{23,24}.

Procedure :

For titrimetric data ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01) was used. The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted in the form of correction factor^{25,26}. For the determination of stability constants of ternary species, initially, strong acid was titrated against alkali at regular intervals to check the completion of the equilibration of the glass electrode. Then, the calomel electrode was refilled with TX100-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. All the titrations were performed in medium containing varying concentrations of TX100-water mixtures (0.0-2.5% v/v) pH metrically at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 cm³. Titrations were carried out in the presence of different relative concentrations of the metal ion to Phe (L) and MA (X) with 0.4 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide. The concentrations of the ingredients are given in Table 1. The details of the experimental procedure and the titration assembly were given elsewhere^{27,28}.

Results and discussion

Titration curves :

For the present work different set of titrations were titrated separately with standard NaOH solution these titration curves are given in Fig. 1. These curves were best evidence for formation of ternary species in the solution.

From this figure reveals that :

- (i) A decrease in pH when the ligand (L/X) is added to the free acid solution suggests that the re-

Table 1. Total initial concentrations of ingredients (in mmol) for mixed ligand titrations in TX100-water mixtures [NaOH] = 0.4 mol L⁻¹; V₀ = 50.0 cm³; temp = 303 K; ionic strength = 0.16 mol L⁻¹; mineral acid = 1 mmol; M = Pb^{II}/Cd^{II}/Hg^{II}; L = Phe; X = MA

% v/v TX100	TM0			TL0		C _M : C _L : C _X
	Pb ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Hg ^{II}	Phe	MA	
0.0	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.2494	0.2498	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
				0.3741	0.3747	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4988	0.4996	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
				0.2495	0.2493	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
0.5	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.3742	0.3739	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4990	0.4986	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
				0.2505	0.2483	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
1.0	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.3757	0.3724	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.5010	0.4966	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
				0.2489	0.2494	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
1.5	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.3733	0.3741	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4878	0.4988	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
				0.2503	0.2488	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
2.0	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.3754	0.3732	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.5006	0.4976	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
				0.2484	0.2478	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
2.5	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.3726	0.3717	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4968	0.4956	1 : 2.5 : 5.0

Fig. 1. Titration curves (M = Hg, L = Phe, X = MA and FA = HNO₃).

lease of protons due to deprotonation of protonated ligands prepared in acidic media (0.05 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃). In this titration curve of MA (X) shows lower pH due to more protons from deprotonation of protonated ligands compared to Phe (L).

- (ii) Metal ligand curves (ML/MX) shows lower pH comparing their protonation curves indicating

formation of metal ligand complex species and release of protons.

- (iii) The mixed-ligand (MLX) curve lie below the pure ligand as well as those of binary metal ligand curves indicating the formation of ternary complex species and release of more protons.
- (iv) Since the mixed-ligand curve did not coincide with either of the individual metal titration curves in the lower pH range, the formation of complex by simultaneous equilibria was inferred.
- (v) The formation of mixed complex species in solution was supported by absence of any solid phase during the titration of ternary mixture.

Modeling of chemical speciation :

A preliminary investigation of alkalimetric titrations of mixtures containing different mole ratios of Phe and MA in the presence of mineral acid and inert electrolyte inferred that no condensed species were formed. Protonation constants of Phe and MA²⁹ and their binary complexes^{30,31} with toxic metals in TX100-water mixture have already been studied in this laboratory. The protonation

constants and the stability constants of the binary metal complexes of these ligands were fixed in refining of ternary complexes and in testing various chemical models using MINQUAD75. The best fit models were chosen based on the statistical parameters³⁰ like χ^2 , *R*-factor, skewness and kurtosis given in Table 2. The ternary complex species detected are MLXH₂, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Pb^{II} and MLX₂H₃, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Cd^{II} and ML₂XH₂, ML₂XH and MLX₂ for Hg^{II}. A very low standard deviation (SD) in log values of overall stability constants (log β) indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in the concentrations of the ligands and the hydrogen ion under experimental conditions) corrected for degrees of freedom, indicate that the models represent the experimental data. Small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of kurtosis and skewness should be three and zero, respectively.

The kurtosis values, in the present study indicate that some of the residuals are nearer to mesokurtic and other form leptokurtic patterns. The values of skewness recorded in Table 2 are between -1.21 and 1.18. This data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution; hence, the least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The suitability of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic *R*-values recorded.

Effect of surfactant on the stability of ternary complexes :

The variation of overall stability constant values with surfactant content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic. Born's classical treatment³² holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. According to this treatment, the energy of electrostatic interaction is related to dielectric constants. Hence, the log β values should vary linearly as a function mole fraction of the surfactant. The effect of surfactant on complex equilibria and apparent shift in the magnitude of stability constants in micellar

Table 2. Parameters of best-fit chemical models of Phe and MA complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} in TX100-water mixtures

% v/v	log β (SD)					pH-range	NP	U_{corr}	χ^2	Skewness	Kurtosis	<i>R</i> -factor
	MLXH ₂	ML ₂ XH	ML ₂ XH ₂	MLX ₂ H ₃	MLX ₂							
TX100												
						Pb ^{II}						
0.0	22.36(20)	22.29(39)	28.71(22)	-	-	4.0-8.7	54	40.49	36.59	1.03	8.18	0.0832
0.5	21.43(11)	22.40(20)	28.70(19)	-	-	4.0-7.0	27	2.083	18.67	-0.04	4.81	0.0103
1.0	21.08(52)	22.47(57)	28.14(57)	-	-	4.0-7.0	32	10	3.25	0.27	2.91	0.0245
1.5	21.46(29)	22.51(38)	28.62(39)	-	-	4.0-7.0	30	6.666	3.47	0.06	2.94	0.0200
2.0	21.49(24)	22.48(23)	28.68(25)	-	-	4.0-7.0	30	8.148	9.07	0.28	4.83	0.0208
2.5	21.67(17)	22.35(39)	28.60(28)	-	-	4.0-7.0	29	4.615	10.62	0.27	4.57	0.0163
						Cd ^{II}						
0.0	-	21.96(39)	28.92(48)	30.55(46)	-	4.0-9.0	55	37.46	22.33	1.18	6.94	0.0829
0.5	-	21.60(29)	28.52(33)	30.01(19)	-	4.0-9.0	34	7.741	7.65	0.18	3.66	0.0210
1.0	-	21.19(36)	28.08(31)	30.43(23)	-	4.0-7.0	25	2.272	2.08	-0.02	3.10	0.0111
1.5	-	21.18(38)	28.26(27)	30.23(17)	-	4.0-7.0	25	3.636	4.32	0.02	2.58	0.0134
2.0	-	21.22(30)	28.33(25)	29.95(24)	-	4.0-7.0	27	5.416	16.53	-0.01	5.90	0.0155
2.5	-	21.43(26)	28.07(19)	29.84(12)	-	4.0-7.0	25	2.272	8.32	0.13	4.90	0.0109
						Hg ^{II}						
0.0	-	22.86(16)	28.52(05)	-	13.44(9)	2.4-6.4	21	0.555	8.00	0.39	3.39	0.0032
0.5	-	24.02(24)	28.80(37)	-	15.25(28)	4.0-6.4	23	2	5.39	0.50	2.53	0.0105
1.0	-	24.14(22)	29.54(25)	-	15.30(18)	4.0-6.4	22	0.526	6.55	0.49	3.42	0.0061
1.5	-	24.85(39)	30.02(46)	-	15.51(38)	4.0-6.4	21	1.111	7.62	0.35	2.81	0.0082
2.0	-	24.69(48)	30.52(45)	-	15.21(39)	4.0-6.4	20	1.176	24.84	-1.21	9.89	0.0075
2.5	-	24.38(51)	30.31(51)	-	15.08(51)	4.0-6.4	21	2.777	13.71	-1.05	6.96	0.0111

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(NP - m) \times 10^8$; NP = Number of points; m = number of constants; SD = standard deviation.

media can be attributed³³ to the creation of a concentration gradient of proton between the interface and the bulk solution. The number of micelles increases with the concentration of surfactant, and oppositely charged ions are concentrated in the Stern layer³⁴. The trend of the stability constant ($\log \beta$) values of the ternary complexes of Phe-MA with mole fraction of TX100-water mixture (Fig. 2) exhibits a linear increasing/decreasing trend. The stability of the complex depends on the polarity of the medium, charge on the Stern layer and the electrostatic attraction or repulsive forces operating between the complex species and the micellar surface. The dielectric constant of the medium decreases with increasing concentration of surfactant^{35,36}. The charged species will be destabilized due to the decreased dielectric constant of the medium with increasing surfactant concentration. The linear increase/decrease indicates the dominant action of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces on the complex equilibria under the present experimental condi-

tions. The non-linearity may be due to considerable contribution from non-electrostatic forces.

Stability of ternary complexes :

Formation of ternary complexes can be represented by the equilibrium given in the eq. (1). The stability constants are calculated from the pH-metric titration curves using equilibrium (2) in the usual way with the help of the computer programme MINIQUAD75³⁷. To calculate the correction factor the computer program SCPHD³⁸ was used. Where β_{pqr} is ternary stability constant, $[M_p L_q X_r H_s]$, $[M]^p$, $[L]^q$, $[X]^r$ and $[H]^s$ are the concentration of ternary complex, metal ion, primary ligand, secondary ligand and proton, respectively. During the refinement of ternary systems, the correction factor, protonation constant and binary formation constant of phenylalanine and maleic were fixed. The variation of stability constants with the mole fraction of the medium was analyzed on the basis of electrostatic/non-electrostatic, solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Fig. 2. Variation of magnitude of stability constant ($\log \beta$) of ternary complexes of Phe-MA with mole fraction ($n_x \times 10^3$) of TX100 : (A) Pb^{II}, (B) Cd^{II}, (C) Hg^{II} : (o) $\log \beta_{ML_2XH}$, (Δ) $\log \beta_{ML_2XH_2}$, (\star) $\log \beta_{MLXH_2}$, (\square) $\log \beta_{MLX_2H_3}$, (\diamond) $\log \beta_{MLX_2}$, respectively.

$$\beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[M_pL_qX_rH_s]}{[M]^p [L]^q [X]^r [H]^s} \quad (2)$$

The change in the stability of the ternary complexes as compared to their binary analogues was quantified based on the difference in stability ($\Delta \log K$) for the reactions ML with X and $M_{(aq)}$ with L and X^{39-44} , where L is the primary ligand (Phe) and X is the secondary ligand (MA). It is compared with that calculated purely on the statistical grounds as given in eq. (3).

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MLX}^M - \log K_{ML}^M - \log K_M^M \quad (3)$$

This corresponds to the equilibrium

where $\log K_{MLX}^M$ is stability for formation of ternary complex from metal ion (M), primary ligand (L) and secondary ligand (X), $\log K_{ML}^M$ is stability for formation of binary complex from metal ion (M) and primary ligand (L), $\log K_{MX}^M$ is stability for formation of binary complex from metal ion (M) and secondary ligand (X).

The electrostatic theory of binary complex formation and statistical arguments suggest the availability of the additional coordination positions of the hydrated metal ion for the first ligand than for the second. Hence, the usual order of stability, $K_{ML}^M > K_{MLX}^M$ applies. This suggests that $\Delta \log K$ to be negative, although several exceptions have been found⁴⁵. The statistical values of $\Delta \log K$ for bidentate L and X are -0.4 and -0.6 for octahedral and square planar complexes, respectively, whereas for distorted octahedral complexes, the values vary between -0.9 and -0.3. The negative values for $\Delta \log K$ can be understood that the secondary ligand forms a more stable complex with ML than the hydrated metal ion. Whenever the experimental values of $\Delta \log K$ exceed the statistical values, it can be inferred that the ternary complex is formed due to the interaction of ML with X or MX with L. $\Delta \log K$ values of ternary complexes are positive for O-donors (malonic acid, pyrocatechol etc.)⁴⁰, negative for N-donors (ethylene diamine) and intermediate or negative for amino acids with both N and O coordination sites^{46,47}. However, a very high negative value (-2.3) for Cu (ethylene diamine) (iminodiacetic acid) and a positive value (0.82) for Cu (O-phen)-(6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-sulphonate) was also observed.

The $\Delta \log K$ values calculated from binary and ternary complexes and the equations for the calculation of $\Delta \log K$ are given in Table 3. These values could not be calculated for some of the systems due to the absence of relevant binary species. In the present study, $\Delta \log K$ values are in the range from -8.52 to 2.61 which indicate that the ternary complexes formed by the Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} were more stable compared to Hg^{II} . The reason for the extra stability of these complexes may be due to (i) the interactions outside the coordination sphere such as the formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands, (ii) charge neutralization, (iii) chelate effect and (iv) stacking interactions^{48,49}.

Table 3. $\Delta \log K$ values of ternary complexes of Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} -Phe and MA in TX100-water mixtures and the corresponding equations used in the calculations

% v/v TX100	$\Delta \log K_{MLXH_2}$	$\Delta \log K_{ML_2XH}^{Pb^{II}}$	$\Delta \log K_{ML_2XH_2}$	$\Delta \log K_{MLXH_2}$
0.0	-4.28	0.61	2.07	-
0.5	-5.72	0.05	1.55	-
1.0	-6.39	0.28	0.67	-
1.5	-5.59	0.73	1.57	-
2.0	-5.79	0.04	1.4	-
2.5	-6.06	-0.6	0.87	-
Cd^{II}				
0.0	-	0.55	2.54	-
0.5	-	-0.06	1.5	-
1.0	-	0.35	1.51	-
1.5	-	-0.43	1.41	-
2.0	-	-0.65	1.08	-
2.5	-	-0.31	1.11	-
Hg^{II}				
0.0	-	0.59	0.43	-8.52
0.5	-	2.13	1.44	-6.21
1.0	-	2.08	1.38	-6.05
1.5	-	2.61	2.09	-6.05
2.0	-	2.44	2.55	-6.28
2.5	-	2.01	1.92	-6.41

Equations for calculation of $\Delta \log K$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \log K_{MLXH_2} &= \log \beta_{MLXH_2} - \log \beta_{ML_2H} - \log \beta_{MX_2H} \\ \Delta \log K_{ML_2XH} &= \log \beta_{ML_2XH} - \log \beta_{ML_2H} - \log \beta_{MX_2} \\ \Delta \log K_{ML_2XH} &= \log \beta_{ML_2XH} - \log \beta_{ML_2H} - \log \beta_{MX_2H} \\ \Delta \log K_{ML_2XH_2} &= \log \beta_{ML_2XH_2} - \log \beta_{ML_2H} - \log \beta_{MX_2H} \\ \Delta \log K_{MLX_2} &= \log \beta_{MLX_2} - \log \beta_{ML_2H} - \log \beta_{MX_2} \\ \Delta \log K_{MLX_2} &= \log \beta_{MLX_2} - \log \beta_{ML_2H} - \log \beta_{MX_3} \end{aligned}$$

Effect of influential parameters on stability constants :

Any variation in the parameters (the concentrations of ingredients) affects the magnitudes of equilibrium constants. Such parameters are called influential parameters. In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the concentrations of alkali, acid, ligands, metal ions, correction factor and volume. The results of typical samples given in Table 4 emphasize that the errors in the concentrations of alkali and acid affect the stability constant more than those of the ligands and metal ion, log *F* and volume.

Table 4. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the stability constants of ternary complexes of Pb^{II} with Phe-MA in 2.5% (v/v) TX100-water mixture

Ingredient	% Error	log β _{mlxh} (SD)		
		1 1 1 2	1 2 1 1	1 2 1 2
Alkali	0	21.67(17)	22.35(39)	28.60(28)
	-5	24.27(22)	Rejected	Rejected
	-2	22.56(11)	21.09(58)	28.77(29)
	+2	22.23(77)	25.18(88)	30.17(89)
	+5	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
Acid	-5	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
	-2	21.67(60)	24.15(72)	29.42(67)
	+2	22.28(11)	21.26(39)	28.48(30)
	+5	23.23(13)	Rejected	Rejected
	Ligand (L)	-5	21.70(16)	22.41(31)
-2		21.68(17)	22.38(33)	28.62(30)
+2		21.66(17)	22.33(32)	28.57(30)
+5		21.64(17)	22.30(32)	28.54(29)
Ligand (X)		-5	21.61(49)	23.53(67)
	-2	21.56(25)	22.77(43)	28.66(40)
	+2	21.82(12)	22.13(26)	28.65(23)
	+5	22.12(09)	21.97(21)	28.88(17)
	Metal	-5	21.61(19)	22.48(35)
-2		21.65(17)	22.40(34)	28.58(31)
+2		21.70(16)	22.31(32)	28.61(29)
+5		21.74(15)	22.25(30)	28.64(28)
log <i>F</i>		-5	21.73(16)	22.23(34)
	-2	21.67(16)	22.22(35)	28.55(30)
	+2	21.64(17)	22.35(33)	28.57(30)
	+5	21.58(18)	22.35(34)	28.52(31)
	Volume	-5	21.65(19)	22.33(40)
-2		21.66(17)	22.34(39)	28.59(28)
+2		21.68(17)	22.36(39)	28.61(28)
+5		21.69(18)	22.37(40)	28.62(29)

Chemical speciation :

Distribution diagrams drawn using the formation constants of the best fit model are shown in Fig. 2 which contain protonated and unprotonated species like MLXH₂, ML₂XH and ML₂XH₂ for Pb^{II} and ML₂XH, ML₂XH₂ and MLX₂H₃ for Cd^{II} and ML₂XH, ML₂XH₂ and MLX₂ for Hg^{II}. The distribution diagrams indicate the relative abundance of various forms of metal ions (chemical speciation) at different pH and dielectric conditions. A stable ternary complex shall be responsible for metal ion transportation in bio-systems and the weak binary metal complexes make the essential metals bioavailable. The increased concentrations of complexing agents make the essential metal ions unavailable due to the formation of stable complexes. The formation of the possible complex species can be represented by the following equilibria :

Some typical distribution diagrams in 0.5% TX100-water mixture are shown in Fig. 3, Fig. 3(A) shows the formation of Pb^{II}-Phe-MA complexes, MLXH₂, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH in the pH range 2.0–9.0, in this range total metal ion participate in bonding. At lower pH the species MLXH₂ had high concentration (Equilibria 4). As the pH increases the concentration of MLXH₂, LH₂⁺ and XH₂

Fig. 3. Species distribution diagrams of ternary complexes of Phe and MA : (A) Pb^{II} , (B) Cd^{II} and (C) Hg^{II} in 0.5% v/v TX100-water mixture.

decreased and the concentration of ML_2XH_2 and ML_2XH were increased (Equilibria 5, 6, 9, 10 and 11). Above pH value 5.0, the concentration of ML_2XH_2 species decreases with increasing ML_2XH species indicates that ML_2XH forms through the (Equilibria 8, 12, 13 and 14).

Fig. 3(B) shows the formation of Cd^{II} -Phe-MA complexes, MLX_2H_3 , ML_2XH_2 and ML_2XH in the pH range 2.0–9.0. At lower pH value the concentration of MLX_2H_3 is high (Equilibria 15). As the pH value increases the concentration of MLX_2H_3 decreases with increasing the concentration of ML_2XH_2 species (Equilibria 5 and 6). Above 5.0 pH value ML_2XH complex formed while the XH_2 and MX_2H species decreased (Equilibria 13 and 14).

Fig. 3(C) shows the formation of Hg^{II} -Phe-MA complexes, ML_2XH_2 , ML_2XH and MLX_2 in the pH range 2.0–8.0. At lower pH the species ML_2XH_2 had high concentration (Equilibria 5 and 6). As the pH increases the concentration of MLX_2H_2 , LH_2^+ and XH_2 decreased and the concentration of ML_2XH is increases (Equilibria 8, 9

and 10). Above pH value 5.0, MLX_2 species has high concentration (Equilibria 16 and 17).

Structures :

Depending upon the nature of the ligands and the metal ions and based on the basic chemical knowledge the structures of the ternary complexes were proposed as shown in Fig. 4. These structures indicate that phenylalanine and maleic acid act as monodentate or bidentate ligands depending upon the pH conditions. In highly acidic medium the amino group of L-phenylalanine is protonated and do not participate in coordination as shown in the structure of MLX_2H_3 , MLXH_2 and ML_2XH_2 . In ML_2XH_2 species phenylalanine act as monodentate and maleic acid acts as bidentate. In mono protonated ternary complexes like ML_2XH , phenylalanine acts as momo and bidentate ligand and maleic acid act as only bidentate and the proton is on phenylalanine but not on maleic acid. So, the species is $\text{M}(\text{L}_2\text{H})\text{X}$ but not $\text{M}(\text{L}_2)(\text{XH})$.

Fig. 4. Proposed structures of ternary complexes of phenylalanine and maleic acid, where S is either solvent or water molecule.

Conclusions

The following conclusions have been drawn from the modeling studies of the speciation of ternary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with phenylalanine and maleic acid in TX100-water media :

- (i) The species detected are MLXH₂, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Pb^{II} and MLX₂H₃, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Cd^{II} and ML₂XH₂, ML₂XH and MLX₂ for Hg^{II}. Where L = Phe and X = MA. Only these species are refined due to the restricted pH ranges and the possible active forms of ligands like LH₂⁺, LH, and XH₂, XH⁻ for Phe and MA, respectively.
- (ii) The values of $\Delta \log K$ indicate that the ternary

species have extra stability compared to the binary species, may be due to the interactions outside the coordination sphere, such as the formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands, charge neutralization, chelate effect, stacking interactions and the electrostatic interaction between non-coordinated charge groups of the ligands.

- (iii) The linear variation in the stabilities of ternary complexes with increasing mole fraction of the surfactant is due to the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces.
- (iv) The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incor-

poration of errors is alkali > acid > maleic acid > phenylalanine > metal ion > log *F* > volume.

- (v) The study also gives an insight into the metal availability/metal transport in biofluids. The ternary complexes are more amenable for "metal transport" because of their extra stability.

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